
D1.1 DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION, COMMUNICATION AND OUTREACH STRATEGY

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1. Introduction

The overarching ambition of CODECS is to improve the collective capacity to understand, assess and foresee the full range of benefits and costs of farm digitalisation, and to build digital ecosystems that maximise the net benefits of digitalisation. It will be done by pursuing the following specific objectives:

1. Mainstreaming the concept of “**sustainable digitalisation**” in the European AKIS and in the wider policy environments.
2. Building the conceptual “system-approach / actor-centred” base for the “sustainable digitalisation” of agriculture and a layered cost-benefit assessment framework.
3. Analysing, and understanding the implications, of the role of different contexts in the generation of costs and benefits of digitalisation through the analysis of “digital ecosystems”.
4. Providing data on the costs and benefits of digitalisation in a variety of European farming contexts, by setting up and carrying out user-friendly assessment methodologies.
5. Setting up demonstrations to scale digital technologies adoption.
6. Developing evidence-based and future-proof policy tools for sustainable digitalisation.
7. Raising awareness and facilitating the uptake of digital technologies for sustainable development through the development of a platform and assessment tools.

The present Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach Strategy (hereafter DECO or the ‘Strategy’) is instrumental to achieving these objectives and is as such integrated into and supporting all the other activities of the project as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. CODECS PERT diagram

The Strategy follows the definitions for the terms Communication, Exploitation, Dissemination and Outreach.

Communication refers to the promotion of the action and results, and it aims at reaching multiple, non-expert audiences.

Dissemination — The public disclosure of the results by appropriate means, other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results, including by scientific publications in any medium.

Exploit(ation) — The use of results in further research and innovation activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including among other things, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

The CODECS DECO Strategy should be understood as a living document. Accordingly, regular updates have been planned to allow it to evolve over time, as a result of new or emerging information, opportunities or trends. It will particularly evolve as part of the process of developing greater coordination and synergies between the work of CODECS, and work of relevant stakeholders on the subject.

2. Objectives of the strategy

The activities presented in this Strategy are those concerning, mostly those of CODECS **Work Package 1 ‘Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach (DECO) strategy’**. In this sense, the specific objectives of this work package are:

- to enable two-way communication between CODECS and its target audiences;
- to develop and implement a Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach (DECO) strategy, to drive actions to amplify project results and maximise its impact;
- to organise, support and coordinate all partners in their DECO activities
- to create, animate and coordinate knowledge sharing and peer-to-peer learning through the CODECS “Knowledge Accelerator”.

The DECO is based on the model that articulates communication and dissemination objectives in a four-step logic. Firstly, the Strategy focuses on **Awareness**, by which target audiences discover the project and why is it relevant. This will happen throughout the whole project implementation, but particularly on the early stages where there are not proper results. Following this, the Strategy will focus on **Understanding**, ensuring that the target understands the key messages emerging from CODECS. Progressively, the Strategy will aim at enhancing **Motivation**, engaging stakeholders and aligning their needs to those of CODECS. Finally, the Strategy will address **Action**, especially by facilitating the uptake of its outcomes and results within and beyond the project’s scope.

Figure 2. CODECS DECO four-step logic

Although this logic can be applied on a linear way (starting by generating awareness about the project and its objectives, and finalising with target audiences effectively using the results), these stages can happen simultaneously. For example, the engagement of stakeholders described on step 3 will be key throughout the whole project implementation.

3. Guiding principles

The Strategy aims to ensure that the concept of "sustainable digitalisation" is mainstreamed into the European AKIS and wider policy environments. The Strategy will therefore not simply inform but promote uptake and action by all stakeholders.

This will require a commitment on the part of the audience to take an active role, which will require giving them compelling evidence, knowledge and tools. In order to achieve impact and stimulate target audiences to interact, all communications activities and products will adhere to the following guiding principles:

- **Specificity.** The activities set in the CODECS Strategy will present facts and information that are digestible and practical for target audiences to implement.

- **Resonance.** Target audiences must feel/see the direct and indirect benefits that they will derive from the outcomes of the project. In order to improve action, the project will show how the results will affect them personally, economically and environmentally, as well as socially and globally.
- **Connectivity.** Using carefully tailored methods and tools to boost engagement and encourage interaction and dialogue, target audiences will share what they are doing while discovering what others are developing, which will act as an inspiration and a driver for mutual learning and knowledge exchange.
- **Results-based approach.** Focused activities to achieve specific, measurable outcomes.
- **Continuous learning.** Diligent research, analysis, execution, and assessment that continuously feeds and improves planning and action. This includes constantly getting stakeholder feedback to improve the Strategy, and also flexibility to adjust the scope and approach to relevant developments over time.
- **Storytelling.** Through storytelling techniques in audiovisual materials, articles, or social media, visibility will be given to the outcomes of the project, as well as the activities the consortium embark on. Dedicated campaigns will also be created to mainstream the concept of “sustainable digitalisation” in the European AKIS and in the wider policy environments.
- **Co-design.** Change cannot be achieved with only a top-down approach. CODECS will involve stakeholders, in particular those involved in the Living Labs, Demo Farms and Knowledge Accelerator, in the co-creation of communication actions. Policy-makers and policy implementers will also be engaged from an early stage of the project through the policy-science interface of the KA. This will provide opportunities for engagement and feedback, as well as tailoring the outputs of the project to the specific needs of each target group. A key to success in stakeholder engagement is to start the discussion with what is important for the target audience and find pathways/solutions within the rural development narrative.
- **Sustainability.** Throughout the CODECS DECO activities, the project will convey sustainability and create economic and social impact. Sustainability will be integrated in campaigns, events, stakeholder dialogues, and reporting.

Open Science

Open science consists in the sharing of knowledge, data and tools as early as possible in the Research and Innovation (R&I) process, in open collaboration with all relevant knowledge actors, including academia, industry, public authorities, end users (farmers and farmers’ advisors), citizens and society at large. CODECS will go beyond the mandatory requirements set in the Grant Agreement to contribute to increasing the quality, efficiency and impact of R&I, lead to greater responsiveness to societal challenges, and increase trust of society in the science system.

In this sense, CODECS will ensure open access to scientific publications under the conditions that are specified in the Grant Agreement. All deliverables, policy briefs and practice abstracts, presentations, will be open access and licenced under the latest version if a Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or an equivalent licence or with CC BY. All scientific publications will be granted immediate access and will be made available through trusted repositories. Authors will retain the needed intellectual property rights to comply with Open Access requirements.

CODECS will adhere to the principle ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’. In this sense, a process of reviewing by the coordinator will be put in place to ensure that IPR, security and privacy rules will be respected before publishing sensitive information.

Given the existing links to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) related initiatives through CNR participation, CODECS will seek interactions and complementarities with the EOSC, and contribute to increasing the level of FAIRness (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability) of research data produced/collected by the project;

CODECS will carry out responsible management of research data in line with the FAIR principles of ‘Findability’, ‘Accessibility’, ‘Interoperability’ and ‘Reusability’, notably through the generalised use of data management plans (see D8.1, 8.2, 8.3 and 8.4 Data Management Plan).

Information about the research outputs/tools/instruments needed to validate the conclusions of scientific publications or to validate/re-use research data will be deposited in trusted repositories.

In addition, CODECS will subscribe to the Rural Digital Europe dashboard (<https://rural-digital-europe.openaire.eu/>) under development by DESIRA. Methodologies will be preregistered under the section 'Exploratory research' on the Centre for Open Science website (<https://osf.io/prereg/>). Publications on Open Research Europe and other open peer review initiatives will be warmly encouraged. In addition, beneficiaries will actively be involved as reviewers in open peer review processes.

4. The DECO task force

A Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach Task Force has been established at the beginning of the project to ensure that all partners are involved in the design and implementation of the DECO strategy. The DECO Task Force is comprised of at least one representative of each partner organization, which can change as the project evolves to better assess the needs of the Strategy. The Task Force is coordinated by AEIDL with the support of UNIFI.

The roles and responsibilities of the DECO Task Force are:

- ensuring the relay of information upwards/downwards;
- reporting the different communication activities carried out by their organisation, as well as their impact (Monitoring Tables);
- identifying and adapt the communication messages to each region;
- identifying the main communication objectives per region/country;
- translating the main dissemination/communication material.

Figure 3. DECO Task Force structure

4.1. Training sessions

Specific training sessions are foreseen for the DECO Task Force. Needs of partners to communicate and disseminate the results of CODECS at local/regional/national level will be assessed, and online or face-to-face training sessions will be organised based on the responses of partners. Training sessions will be recorded and circulated with the consortium as video tutorials for further issue throughout the project development.

Table 1. Preliminary list of training sessions

Session	Estimated date
Working methods/procedures to use DECO channels/tools for internal and external communication.	M9

Session	Estimated date
Social media: how to communicate with local stakeholders through online channels	M9
Media relations and press releases: how to engage the media	M9
How to reach our target audiences and communicate widely about Demo Farm events, before and after demonstrations	M9
Engaging content: story-telling techniques	M12
How to organise an impactful on Farm and Virtual demonstration event	M12
Pitching CODECS: How to captivate the audience at events and conferences	M12
Practice abstracts: how to write short, engaging content for practitioners	M22, M28, M38

Final list of sessions will be defined as the needs of the consortium are assessed or new urgent needs arise during the implementation.

4.2. Guidelines for partners

The project will entail an intense learning activity within the consortium and with its external circles. A series of guidelines for project communications will ensure the quality of the material produced within the project. Guidelines are initially addressed to project partners, and they intend to provide them with guidance, tools, recommendations, and occasionally document templates for a smooth performance and quality result regarding the outputs of the project (See Annex III).

5. Target audiences

5.1. Geographical coverage

Regarding the geographical coverage, the Strategy will be implemented in all EU Member States (MS) and partner countries involved in the CODECS project. When implementing the Strategy, CODECS will consider national differences and local stakeholders and aim at ensuring a balanced and inclusive approach. At a secondary level, CODECS will try to engage with other non-EU MS that are relevant to the project.

For this purpose, CODECS will rely on partner networks, and their knowledge of the local environment. To overcome the language barrier, key materials will be translated to the languages of the project.

5.2. Stakeholder mapping and analysis

In light of the specific project objectives described in Section 2, the Strategy targets the following categories of stakeholders, considered relevant for the achievement of the project goals:

- Scientific community, including researchers included in the CODECS consortium, and others.
- Farmers and farmers' advisors
- Technology developers/providers
- Research and Innovation networks
- Investors

- Policy-makers and public authorities: policy and programme designers and implementers; political decision-makers; policy evaluators; at local, regional, national and EU level.
- Media
- General audience, particularly rural dwellers and communities across Europe.

To ensure the correct delivery of CODECS messages to target audiences, these have been categorised into primary (key to achieving CODECS objectives, and relevant for the DECO goals), secondary (which can support the achievement of the objectives) and tertiary audiences. This categorisation has been done in collaboration with the DECO Task Force (see

Annex I. Results of CODECS DECO Task Force meeting) and will be evaluated periodically. As the needs of the project change, as well as the different phases/logic of DECO start (e.g., understanding will start when there are concrete results), this classification may change. A new evaluation is foreseen for each update of the Strategy.

→ **Primary audiences:** farmers and farmers’ advisors, scientific community, Research and Innovation networks, policy-makers and public authorities.

→ **Secondary audiences:** technology developers/providers, investors, students, rural businesses ad SMEs

→ **Tertiary audiences:** civil society groups, journalists and media.

By considering the relevance of the stakeholders for the project, consulted with the CODECS DECO Strategy, the Strategy establishes different levels of engagement, classifying them in the alignment/influence–interest matrix (Figure 3 below) according to their relative positioning and to the need to collaborate with them, to involve, to inform and/or to consult them. There are three dimensions to the matrix:

Alignment: The extent to which the stakeholder agrees with CODECS’ goals and approach.

Interest: The extent to which the stakeholder is already engaged in the issues or the field of CODECS (e.g., are they committing resources, speaking out, setting objectives)

Influence: The degree to which the stakeholder can sway the debate.

High influence / high interest and low influence / low interest are classic boundary partners.

High influence / low interest would be stakeholders that works in the same broad area as the project, but with different specific objectives.

Low influence/ high interest would be a stakeholder that broadly shares the same objective but does not have the availability to invest time and resources in the project.

Figure 4 Stakeholder mapping by influence and interest

5.3. Multipliers

This Strategy aims at achieving a maximum impact with controlled spending by selecting channels that are the most effective in reaching out to the various target groups and building upon multipliers, namely consortium partners and relevant stakeholders at EU, national, regional and local levels, which can contribute to maximising the potential audience of CODECS. Multipliers will be invited to share the core messages, practices and ultimately the results of the project using their own communications channels, and tools.

A preliminary list of networks, initiatives, projects and relevant organisations that can act as multipliers can be found on section Existing networks, projects and initiatives.

6. Key Messages

CODECS key messages will be adapted to each target audience, and will be refined and updated over the course of the project. A dedicated session was organised at CODECS first General Assembly (December 2022) to validate and co-create project messages involving all the partners.

A first set of messages was included in the proposal phased, which was discussed and refined in the first DECO Task Force meeting. The key messages will be evaluated and updated in specific sessions during the lifespan of the project.

- Digitalisation is not sustainable per se. To contribute to sustainability, it should be framed by the principles of sustainable digitalisation.
- Digitalisation should be a horizontal, cross-cutting issue for any policy, as it happens with sustainability and environmental issues. No matter what is done, how digitalisation affects it should be considered.

- Cost-benefits analyses provide better prospects for farmers about the advantages and disadvantages of digitalisation.
- Living Labs offer engagement to further improve knowledge, skills and resources in cooperation within the community.
- Technology development should be tailored to the conditions of the context to which they apply and innovation should be co-designed.
- Agricultural digitalisation, if inspired to the principles of sustainable digitalisation, will have positive effects on the environment, on society, on the economy.
- Sustainable digitalisation principles will inspire a policy framework and policy tools that will increase the capacity to design sustainable digitalisation strategies.
- CODECS will show, through evidence and science-backed opinions, that sustainable digitalisation of agriculture is possible.

7. DECO Channels

7.1. Website

The website will be the primary hub of information from CODECS, providing a 'one-stop shop' for resources, news, and key information on relevant initiatives; and it will be linked from the rest of communication and dissemination materials produced under the framework of the project. Work on the website will continue throughout the project, incorporating sections and content as soon as it becomes available and taking account arising needs.

The website will be hosted on www.horizoncodecs.eu and will provide an overview of the project, its deliverables and partners. In a dedicated part of the homepage the latest news and articles/blog posts on the project activities will be showcased, as well as all relevant project events.

The webpage will host all digital tools produced by CODECS and will provide a point of reference for farmers, AKIS actors and policy-makers in the field of assessment of digital technologies. There will be a dedicated section for the Knowledge Accelerator (KA) and another one for the CODECS Digital Platform.

Visitors will be given the opportunity to digitally sign-up to the newsletter and they will also be notified of the use of cookies by the website. The CODECS website will be offered in English and translated in at least the languages of the consortium partners through an automated tool embedded on the website.

The website is coded using Wordpress as leading content management system. All monitoring of use (e.g., statistics for periodic reporting to the EC) will be GDPR compliant.

The website will comply with best practice in design for ensuring user accessibility (e.g., colour, font, text formatting) to respect the capabilities of readers and contributors (complying with EC Information Providers Guides; <http://ec.europa.eu/ipg>).

7.2. Social media

The purpose of using social media is to make the project known to potential users, our audience, and to encourage them to participate in the project by accessing its outputs. It will be set up and used as key interactive promotional tools to receive feedback from target stakeholders, accelerate the discussion and to engage them in dialogue.

Social media accounts will be used to communicate and disseminate the project's activities in order to create spaces for discussion and sharing with the audience, the different project actors and potential stakeholders. The content shared on each platform will include different types of outputs and will redirect and feed traffic to the main website.

- **Twitter:** this channel is used for short news flashes, using a clear and crisp style, not too descriptive or institutional. It will also play an important role during events, where live tweeting will be enabled. Live tweeting will

participate in creating a knowledge community linking participants, panel and experts, as well as audiences following the event remotely. Hashtags specific to the project will be created in order to communicate on the different products e.g. #CODECSNews, #CODECSEvent.

- **Facebook:** this channel will be adopted for public outreach and showcasing outputs. Events and Photo album functionalities will be exploited.
- **LinkedIn:** this channel will be used to promote cooperation and support matchmaking between stakeholders and a wide audience of professional stakeholders. Selected articles, news pieces, digital stories and other communications content will also be shared on this platform.
- **YouTube:** the dedicated YouTube channel will be used to publish and collect all the project's multimedia products. Videos will be embedded via YouTube on the website, and easily shared on social media through short links.

Supporting visual material will be used in different social media channels in order to highlight messages. In general, appealing visuals will help catch the attention of the followers/audience, and invite them to read more and learn more about the proposed topic. The illustrative elements, such as banners for social media profiles, will help create a brand consistency and a visual identity for the project. The communication team will assess the suitability to use additional and new social media platforms for the benefit of the project (e.g., TikTok or other similar platforms).

7.3. Newsletter

An online newsletter will be designed and published two times a year, which means 8 newsletters during the whole project. It will provide knowledge and added value content to target groups (see point 5 of the document) from the local, regional, national and EU levels. A key objective is to promote the knowledge and information related to the project and the topic of the project (agricultural digitalisation).

In addition to being a key dissemination channel for relevant information, the external newsletter is a communication product in itself, which will be distributed through three channels:

- **CODECS distribution email list:** With the publication of each newsletter, an email will be sent to all the people who subscribed to the newsletter via the website (involved actors and external audiences).
- **Website:** All newsletters will be stored in a dedicated section on the website, which is accessible to all stakeholders.
- **Social Media:** Dedicated posts will be published in the relevant social media channels (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, etc.).

The newsletter will include content shared on a regular basis by the partners, researchers and other relevant stakeholders, and compiled and sent out through the email marketing platform Sendinblue. The storage and use of personal data of external and internal actors will be done in accordance with the GDPR (see CODECS Data Management Plan for further details).

7.4. Knowledge Accelerator

CODECS' Knowledge Accelerator (KA) is a network that will carry out an organised set of activities based on multi-faceted and transversal approach, and which illustrates an ambition to boost the co-creation of knowledge. It will ease the access to the CODECS outputs by connecting stakeholders and organising specific activities (thematic webinars, briefings, summer online course) aimed at disseminating the CODECS results.

The KA organises spaces for stakeholder exchanges and peer-to-peer learning to 'accelerate' action through capacity building, to maximise the reach of outcomes of the project to external actors. The KA is articulated into three pillars, that will support achieving the project objectives:

- a) a Science-Policy Interface;
- b) a Demonstration Working Group;

c) an AKIS network.

The Work Plan of the KA will be developed from M8 onwards, in consultation with the CODECS Steering Committee and the coordinators of each strand of the KA. It will be included in the next update of this Strategy.

7.5. CODECS Platform

The CODECS platform will serve as a single-point-of-access for some key CODECS results, such as the meta-inventory of digital technologies; toolkits for digital technology impact assessment and sustainability performance demonstration, and virtual reality videos and interactive storybooks. It will also hold the database created to store the data coming from the digital ecosystem analysis (WP3), Cost and Benefit assessment (WP4) and Cost and Benefit demonstrations (WP5) as well as the CODECS methodology playbook.

Therefore, the CODECS platform will act as a key dissemination tool for several outputs of the project.

7.6. General and specialised media

The purpose of using general and specialised media content is to reach both the general public and a more specific audience with key information in the field of digitalisation of agriculture and rural areas.

We will use partners' existing media contact list to develop and implement press and public relation activities. They are encouraged to contact the media (either general or specialised) in order to increase the project's visibility and to spread the activities and results foreseen in it. This can be achieved by:

- The emission of press releases and news. These written pieces will be translated into local languages where relevant in order to engage local stakeholders.
- Inviting media to the main CODECS events, in Brussels as well as in other countries, regions and municipalities. A dedicated press kit will be developed to help partners in the elaboration of their press releases or to help all journalists participating in CODECS events with the elaboration of articles about the project.
- A dedicated training session will be held with CODECS partners in order to support them regarding their media activities at local, regional or national level.

In addition, there is a wealth of valuable EC resources that can serve as amplifiers and multipliers of the CODECS results that are relevant to EU citizens, such as:

- Cordis Results in Brief
- CORDIScovery podcasts
- Research & innovation success stories
- Horizon Magazine
- The R&I Days

7.7. Scientific Journals

The industrial and academic partners will individually and collaboratively publish and present scientific advances in technical papers as well as in peer-reviewed journals. This dissemination activity addresses thus the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) principle "increase access to scientific results" and targeted mainly at the scientific community.

Publications in specialised magazines and papers sent to related events will attract the attention of researchers and practitioners. Joint publications will be encouraged, and an ad-hoc working group within the consortium, composed of WP leaders, will be set up to coordinate participation at scientific conferences.

A preliminary list of targeted journals/magazines is available below:

- European review of Agricultural Economics,
- Agriculture and Human Values,
- Sociologia Ruralis,
- Journal of Rural Studies,
- Sustainability,
- Land Use Policy,
- Agriculture and Food Economics,
- European Journal of Forest Research,
- Agribusiness.

Zenodo

CODECS has set up a community in Zenodo, managed and curated by the project coordinator. Zenodo will be used to effectively deposit and share project outputs, and institutional and community repositories will be used as necessarily. This will ensure that CODECS provides digital or physical access to the results needed to validate the conclusions of scientific publications.

7.8. External events

CODECS plans to have project presentations at scientific conferences targeting relevant domains for the project. Presentations at this kind of event will help the project achieve a high impact, especially among some target groups such as scientists, industrial experts and representatives of international and national public authorities.

Workshops, meetings and other large events (summer and winter schools for academic students, scientific exhibitions, trade fairs, showcases, ICT OPEN DAYS) represent relevant and important opportunities for CODECS dissemination. All this complies with the RRI principle to increase access to scientific results. The goal of these events will be to disseminate both the techniques developed during the project and the preliminary results of the project to targeted beneficiaries.

The CODECS target conferences and events are summarised in the table below, which will be continuously updated during the regular communications meetings, with newly identified events.

Table 2. Preliminary list of third-party events where CODECS could be presented

Event	Website
Rural Pact Conference	https://rural-vision.europa.eu/index_en
European Week of Regions and Cities	https://europa.eu/regions-and-cities/
EU Green Week	https://environment.ec.europa.eu/events/eu-green-week-2023-2023-06-06_en
European Society of Rural Sociology Congress	https://esrs2023.institut-agro-rennes-angers.fr/
EAAE European Association of Agricultural economics Congress	https://eaae.org/default.aspx
IFSA International Farming Systems Association 2024	https://ifsa.boku.ac.at/cms/index.php?id=2
DESIRA Final Conference	https://desira2020.eu/desira-final-conference/
European Startup Village Forum	
SMART VILLAGE forum	https://smartvillageevents.com/en/smart-village-forum/
2nd Project Management Board Meeting in the Netherlands (it could happen online) (June 2023)	https://icaerus.eu/
QUANTIFARM Project meeting	https://quantifarm.eu/
SIA (International Agricultural Show) in France	https://www.salon-agriculture.com/
SPACE (International Livestock Show) in France	https://www.space.fr/

Event	Website
SITEVI (International exhibition of equipment and know-how for vine-wine, olive and fruit & vegetable production)	https://en.sitevi.com/
SIVAL (Plan Production Trade Show)	https://www.sival-angers.com/en/sival/le-salon/

In addition, CODECS will aim to participate in other third-party events related to the sustainable digitisation of agriculture, such as those organised by European and national networks such as the CAP Network, the Rural Pact, in which active participation will be encouraged in order to present the outcomes of the projects (e.g., key messages).

7.9. Existing networks, projects and initiatives

CODECS will rely on the existing networks of project partners, past and current projects, and relevant initiatives at national and EU level

Table 3. List of existing networks, project and initiatives of interest for CODECS

Name of initiative/project	Website	Target group
Agriculture of Data Partnership	https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/horizon-cl6-2023-governance-01-1	Researchers, technicians, policy-makers, practitioners, businesses, farmers, end users
Rural Pact	https://rural-vision.europa.eu/index_en	Public authorities, civil society organisations, businesses, citizens, academic and research and innovation networks and organisations.
Broadband Competence Offices Network	https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/bco-network	
CAP Networks	https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/index_en	
SmartAgriHubs Innovation Portal	https://www.smartagrihubs.eu/login	
GAIA-X Network	https://www.data-infrastructure.eu/GAIA-X/Navigation/EN/Home/home.htm	Companies, researchers, Data Owners, Farmers, Industry
Data4Food (Horizon Europe 2021)	https://data4food2030.eu/project/direct/	
AgriDataSpace (Digital Europe 2022)	https://agridataspace-csa.eu/	Companies, researchers, Data Owners, Farmers, Industry
ICAERUS		Companies, researchers, Data Owners, Farmers, Industry
FARMTOPIA		Companies, researchers, Data Owners, Farmers, Industry
AgriFoodTEF	https://www.agrifoodtef.eu/	
QuantiFarm	https://quantifarm.eu/	
Oper-8	https://www.oper-8.eu/	
BEATLES	https://beatles-project.eu/	

8. DECO activities and materials

CODECS will develop targeted products that will be communicated through the relevant channels described above. These products are designed in a way to maximise its usefulness for the targeted audience.

8.1. Visual identity

A logotype and style guide have been created to serve as a guide for the visual identity of CODECS. This Style Guide indicates all the indications and rules of use of the CODECS brand, which will be used in all external communications, at local, national and EU level. The CODECS visual identity aims at making the project recognisable by all our target audiences.

The brand guidelines define the chosen typography for editorial and visual materials, the colour palette that will define the project and finally the logo that will unite the heart of the project with the defined visual identity. It will also include integration with the EU emblem and photographic manipulation. Based on the defined visual identity, the following communication elements will be created, and made available with the DECO Task Force:

The visual identity guide (see

Annex II. CODECS Visual Identity guidelines) includes all the guidelines, rules and recommendations for perpetuating the CODECS brand identity in all external and internal communications. In particular, it defines the use of the logo, the use of colour, fonts, correct usage and integration with EU emblem, and photo manipulation.

- Visual identity in several formats.
- Social media banners
- Template for the newsletter
- Template for Deliverables
- Template for PowerPoint presentations
- Templates for News items
- Templates for Policy Briefs and Practice Abstracts
- Visuals for multimedia material (e.g., videos)
- Event material
 - Roll-ups
 - Name tags
 - Leaflet
 - Other materials on needs

Special attention will be given to the colour combination of the final communication products to address the needs of colour sensitive audiences (e.g., colour blinded), enabling a better comprehension of the information, in particular in those elements such as graphs and figures that present information using different colour combinations.

8.2. News items

One of the key webpages within the CODECS site will be the News & Events section. This section will include short, concise, informative news items that present developments of the project (including those emerging from the Living Labs), as well as developments happening at European level that are of interest to the CODECS target audiences.

This will be done by keeping up to date with events, achievements and result, emerging both from the project itself, key stakeholders, and initiatives at EU level.

This section will be regularly updated and fed with contributions from the Communication team (AEIDL) and project partners (through the DECO Task Force). They will be published in the different communication channels of the project as a source of information and to try to create feedback with the public.

8.3. Blog articles

By using the website as the main source of information for the project, a specific section will be created to store and share relevant, longer, in-depth blog posts and articles. Rural stakeholders and consortium partners can write blog articles on a specific topic of interest to the project. The aim is to share knowledge and that are of interest to CODECS partners as well as external stakeholders. These articles will be widely promoted through CODECS social media and included in the foreseen newsletter.

The blog section of the website will allow CODECS to create opportunities for interactive engagement, debates and exchanges amongst stakeholders about specific news, experiences, events, topics of interest for the project or linked to Living Labs' activities and topics.

8.4. Videos and multimedia

Different long and short videos will be produced and edited to suit the different DECO channels. Different formats and elements will be used according to the purpose (animation, stock footage, interviews, etc.), depending on the channel to be disseminated and target audience in mind. Teasers (~10 seconds long) will be produced to be shared on social media as well.

The narrative will be inclusive, and convey key messages targeted to the specific audience, such as policy-makers, farmers and farmers', advisors, researchers, stakeholder associations and networks at EU, national and regional levels through which there is high potential for replication. The script of the videos will be co-created by the DECO Task Force, and AEIDL will provide guidelines on how to improve storytelling. Videos will be produced in English, although interviews with Living Lab members will be recorded in their national/regional language and include subtitles in English. Partners can translate the script of the videos, so they can also include subtitles in the languages of the countries of the consortium. All video material will be placed on the YouTube channel of the project and accessible as well from the project website.

A preliminary set of videos is suggested in the table below.

Table 4. Preliminary list of videos

Content	Duration	Goal	Format
CODECS aims and partners	1-3 min	Introduce the project and its objectives	Stock footage about farm digitalisation, and key messages onscreen.
CODECS Living Labs	~1 min	Present the LLs of the project	Interviews with LLs members and/or coordinators.
CODECS Demo Farms	~1 min	Present the Demo Farms	Interviews with Demo Farms members

In addition to videos and animations produced to achieve the DECO goals, CODECS will also develop Virtual Reality videos as part of WP5. These materials will allow virtual tour enhancement will give to demonstration farms the opportunity to design their own virtual tours and widen the access to on-farm demonstration.

Apart from videos, other multi-media formats will be used according to the project needs. Infographics showcasing key results of the project will be produced for deliverables.

8.5. Webinars

Webinars will be organised to foster an interactive learning environment in which stakeholders feel involved. Webinars are part of the Knowledge Accelerator foreseen activities, and will support targeted audiences to take ownership and be involved in the project. At least 8 webinars are planned throughout the project implementation (at least two per year, with the exception of the first year in which not many results will be available). Expected webinars are:

1. The principles of sustainable digitalisation
2. Digital ecosystems: definitions and examples
3. RRI-based design of farm digital technologies: modelling socio-technical processes
4. Co-benefits and costs of digitalisation in agriculture: evidence from Europe
5. Measuring costs and benefits of digitalisation in agriculture

6. Policies for sustainable digitalisation
7. The role of AKIS for sustainable digitalisation
8. Demonstrating farm digitalisation

The final list of expected webinars will be included in the Knowledge Accelerator work plan, including tentative dates for organisation and target audiences. This will be included in the next update of the Strategy.

8.6. Scientific publications

Scientific publications will be the principal means of disseminating findings to scientific audiences. Partners will publish at least 20 Scientific Publications - either joint publications, special issues, contribution to Scientific Conferences, etc. Open access to scientific publications will be ensured. All scientific publications will be granted immediate access and will be made available through trusted repositories, i.e. Zenodo (see section 7.7 Scientific Journals).

8.7. Practice abstracts and policy briefs

A total of 60 practice abstracts will be produced during the project, coming from WP3, WP4 and WP5. In this sense, 20 Practice Abstracts will be produced about socio-technical process models, 20 Practice Abstracts will deal with demonstrations, and a final set of 20 Practice Abstracts will be done on costs and benefits of digitalisation.

In addition to the EIP Common Format excel file, CODECS will produce short and visually attractive factsheets to showcase the content of the Practice Abstracts. AEIDL will prepare a template for each batch of PAs, and will be responsible for editing and proofreading, finalising the layout and ensuring consistency across the publications. WP leaders will be responsible for providing the content.

Policy briefs aim at strengthening the capacity to design policies for sustainable digitalisation. CODECS will produce at least 14 policy briefs, based on the results of WP2-WP6, following a simple and attractive layout.

These documents will focus on the following topics:

1. Conceptual basis of sustainable digitalisation
2. Digital ecosystems for sustainable digitalisation of farming
3. The role of AKIS in digital ecosystems
4. Demonstration and assessment of digital technologies
5. Analysing farmers' motivations regarding digitalisation
6. An assessment grid for digital technologies
7. Process modelling for sustainable digitalisation in agriculture
8. Policy tools for agricultural digitalisation
9. Economic co-benefits and costs of digitalisation
10. Environmental co-benefits and costs of digitalisation
11. Social co-benefits and costs of digitalisation
12. Co-benefits and costs of digitalisation: a synthesis
13. Digital ecosystems conduciveness: concepts and indicators
14. The gender dimension of farm digitalisation

Practice abstracts and policy briefs will be translated into partners' national languages.

8.8. Press releases

Press releases will be designed and published before CODECS public events and webinars, to attract journalists, linking project activities with relevant media stories. They will focus on significant events and developments. Press contacts will be obtained from partners, in particular from the AEIDL database of journalists. Press kits will be provided to all journalists participating in CODECS events, presenting the project, the partners and key facts/figures. Press kits will be sent before the event in digital format and will be handed out at the events.

8.9. Final Conference

An interactive final CODECS conference will be organised at the end of the project. The final conference will provide a synthesis of the main policy and practice-oriented findings of the project, serving to increase the visibility of the project, foster the exploitation of results, and present it to the general public, target groups and relevant stakeholders. This international event is therefore targeted mainly at policy-makers, media and NGOs.

The details about the final conference (location, venue, organisation, specific themes and objectives, target audience and participants) will be laid out in a Concept Note to facilitate understanding among partners. The monitoring and coordination of it will be undertaken by an event organisation team within the CODECS DECO Task Force, in collaboration with the project coordinator.

The event will be tailored around maximising interaction between participants under the principles of design thinking, co-creation, visual and innovative reporting techniques, as well as the interconnection between offline and online audiences. Tools such as live tweeting and instant surveys or real time visualisation will help to create a knowledge community, as well as audience following the event through social media and, if possible, live streaming. All conference materials will be open source, publicly available through the CODECS website. All materials of the events will comply with best practice in ethical requirements and regulations (e.g., GDPR).

9. Exploitation

CODECS outputs will be open access, available on the CODECS platform, so their uptake will be strongly encouraged. Exploitation will be planned in three main domains: i) Policy; ii) Industry, namely, technology development; and iii) Society, namely AKIS.

9.1. Key exploitable results

CODECS KER	Exploitation Route	Target groups
D2.2 Conceptual framework	Further research activities	Researchers
D2.3 Methodology handbook	Further research activities	Researchers
D3.2 Assessment of digital ecosystems	Further research activities	Researchers
D3.3 Comp. Assessment of digital ecosystems	Use for policy evaluation	Stat. offices, evaluators
D4.4 Report on Costs and Benefits	Further research activities	Researchers
D5.3 Handbook of demonstration	Creating and providing a service	Farmers' advisors
D6.2 Policy environments for digitalisation	Use for policy strategies	Policymakers
D6.3 Policy recommendations and toolbox	Adoption in official acts	Policymakers, Evaluators
D7.9 Digital technology assessment toolkit	Creating and providing a service	Farmers' advisors
D7.5 CODECS platform	Creating and providing a service	Farmers' advisors
D8.7 Report about the Living Lab setup	Further research activities	Researchers, Farmers' advisors

9.2. Exploitation routes (policy, industry, society)

Policy

The Policy Analysis and Roadmap (WP6) has been designed to link to relevant policy needs. The Science-Policy Interface will involve policymakers in the process of design, accelerating the uptake. Some of the partners' experience in projects such as DESIRA and SHERPA in relation to the LTVRA has shown that a strong attention to current policy developments and intense communication with EU policy officers can open opportunities for exploitation already before the end of the project.

Contacts with the Joint Research Centre will be taken to check the possibility to integrating research results and data in databases, and to validate the performance of the indicators developed. National Statistical offices will be contacted for the implementation of CODECS indicators. Living Labs will involve policy-makers at national/regional level to boost exploitation in the implementation phase (statistics, policy evaluation, regional schemes). A specific attention will be dedicated to evaluators' community through collaboration with the Evaluation Helpdesk.

Society

About advisory services, the tools developed by WP7 available on the CODECS platform will be open and complete with documentation and user guides. In all three domains, demonstrations (WP5) and the activities of the Knowledge Accelerator will raise awareness and motivate to uptake.

Industry

CODECS will also explore other exploitation domains, such as certification of data and of technological systems, to explore the potential use of its assessment tools together with technology developers and their associations. On-farm tests will upgrade existing open-source hardware and software.

9.3. Exploitation initiatives

Finally, while dissemination of CODECS Knowledge and outcomes is important, specific measures have been set out for ensuring the maximum possible long-term impact of the project work. Consequently, with the objective of exploiting the results accordingly, several initiatives and exploitation activities will be launched.

In the first place, a CODECS Exploitation Strategy will be further co-developed with the project's partners in the later stages of the project (foreseen in M40) For that purpose, WP leaders and if necessary, other consortium members, will attend a workshop on the exploitation of the project's results. The workshop will cover the definitive identification of the project's KER and the guidelines for the co-design of exploitation routes. External actors engaged through the Living Labs might also be invited, to identify potential synergies and capitalise on the results of CODECS. The CODECS exploitation workshop will be complemented by an online survey of individual exploitation plans which will contribute to the final version of the Exploitation Strategy, included within the DECO Strategy and implementation report final of M46.

In the second place, the sustainability and exploitation of the project's results will be implemented parallelly with the development of open-source toolkits, which will be fully available for users. In this sense, instruments such as the D6.3 Policy recommendation and toolbox and the D7.7 Digital technology assessment and demonstration toolkit will be available to ensure that end-users take advantage of and use the developed tools during and after the end of the project.

Consequently, the sum generated by the open tools for posterior users and the Exploitation Strategy covering knowledge transference through conferences, lessons, peer review articles, policy recommendations, face-to-face meetings with policymakers and other activities, will ensure the durability of the projects and the correct exploitation of its results.

10. Monitoring, evaluation and update

Monitoring and evaluation throughout the life-cycle of CODECS will enable the DECO team to identify what approaches are working (and why) and demonstrate the value of the approach selected for the Strategy. Insights coming from continuous monitoring will be the basis for the annual updates of the Strategy and its targets.

10.1. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Indicators of success will inform the progress towards achieving project objectives. The table below gathers the proposed list of Key Performance Indicators, as well as the expected targets to be achieved by the end of the project.

Table 5. Key Performance Indicators and targets

Key communication output	KPI	Target (Month 48)
Website	No of unique visitors	20 000
	No of downloads of documents from the CODECS website	2 000
	No page views on CODECS website	50 000
Social Media	No of Twitter followers	1 000
	No of LinkedIn followers	200
	No of likes on Facebook	200
	No of Social Media impressions/reach	20 000
	No of videos viewed in YouTube	1 000
Newsletter	No of subscribers	350
Blog	No of views	2 500

The above targets are to be reached by the end of the project, and might need to be adapted according to the results of the internal evaluations of the Strategy.

10.2. Monitoring and assessing communications

The effectiveness of the Strategy will be monitored and assessed using a multichannel, impact measurement framework and digital analytics platforms to gain a holistic view of cross-channel communications. This method combines four kinds of datasets:

- Web Analytics (qualitative and quantitative data from the campaign websites, looking at audience, acquisition and user behaviour);
- Social Media Analytics (performance and the effectiveness of the social media channels);
- Online Listening (impact of communication messages in the online public sphere and the extent to which these messages have seeded online conversations). These conversations may be featured in social networks, websites, blogs;
- Communication and Dissemination monitoring tool (an online tool to be provided by AEIDL to keep track of all the communication activities developed by the consortium, as well as the impact reached in terms of number of readers / attendees to a conference, etc.).

10.3. Regular reporting and Strategy updates

It is essential to retain a reasonable degree of flexibility to adjust scope and methods for the Strategy if finer tailoring of activities for dissemination and awareness-raising becomes necessary as they progress, and once project outcomes and results begin to materialise.

The project periodic reviews with the EC are scheduled for Months 18 and 36, with a final review in Month 48. The reviews will assess project achievements compared to project plans and the Grant Agreement and explain and justify any deviations from the plan. Linking to the reports to be submitted to the EC during the expected reviews, an update of the DECO Strategy will be produced. These updates will consist of four distinct sections: dissemination, communication, exploitation, and a report linked to the Knowledge Accelerator activities. These updates will provide a short overview of the activities developed within each category, as well as review of KPIs and targets, DECO goals, key messages and proposed activities, if considered appropriate.

Further modifications to the Strategy might be carried out to address urgent issues, as appropriate, in response to feedback gathered from the EC, the partners, and users/participants.

11. Risks and contingency plan

The contingency plan is implemented and monitored by the communications team, in close relation to UNIFI as project coordinator. It feeds the project’s reporting duties and ensures that proper and immediate follow-up steps are taken to mitigate or solve the issue. Table 5Table 6 shows a list of identified risks related to the DECO activities, as well as prevention or mitigation measures to minimise them.

Table 6. Contingency plan

Critical risk	Level of risk	Prevention (P) or Mitigation (M) measures
A new pandemic wave.	Medium	(M) The consortium will adapt the activities to an online environment, making sure proper facilitation is ensured for interactive activities such as online workshops, webinars, etc.
There is a gap between communications and research activities.	Medium	(P) AEIDL, as WP leader will encourage researchers to discuss and co-produce the main messages. Templates for communication outputs will be provided.
Research results are too complex to be communicated.	Medium	(P) AEIDL, as WP leader will encourage researchers to discuss and co-produce the main messages. (M) Needs for training in communication will be identified, and capacity-building activities will be organised.
Lack of English language skills in target audiences.	Medium	(P) Some budget has been allocating to translating key materials into other languages. The use of visual communication materials, as well as clear, simple and direct language will facilitate the understanding by target audiences. (M) Use of digital translation tools will be fostered in case lack of resources does not allow for translations.
The economic and social situation shifts the attention of farmers from innovation to other priorities	Medium	(P) CODECS key messages will be co-created with the consortium to ensure relevance. (M) The DECO Taskforce will periodically review the messages from CODECS to ensure they are aligned with the priorities of target audiences.
Partners are not involved in delivering DECO activities at regional/national level	Low	(P) Each partner has to nominate a contact person in charge of communications. The DECO Taskforce set up to coordinate communications efforts
Project fails to meet the target KPI values for the different communication actions (number of RDF members, social media engagement, number of scientific articles, website traffic, etc.)	Low	(P)The partners will establish SMART target values for the different KPIs developed to avoid this risk. (M) In case of bad performance in a specific indicator, a tailored Action Plan will be devised by the communications team.

Annex I. Results of CODECS DECO Task Force meeting

Annex II. CODECS Visual Identity guidelines

(See below)

CODECS

BRAND |
GUIDELINES

LOGO Colours

We have a select set of primary colours and secondary colours.

In the majority of uses, we want strong contrast between all of the colours used.

Primary colours

CMJN
45 12 90 1

PMS
7744 C

RVB
160 182 60

HEX
#a0b63c

CMJN
88 58 0 0

PMS
285 C

RVB
28 100 182

HEX
#1c64b6

CMJN
0 0 0 0

PMS
WHITE

RVB
255 255 255

HEX
#ffffff

Secondary colours

CMJN
88 40 0 0

PMS
Medium Blue C

RVB
0 124 194

HEX
#007cc2

CMJN
34 0 73 0

PMS
374 C

RVB
188 211 100

HEX
#bcd364

CMJN
5 25 91 0

PMS
116 C

RVB
244 192 30

HEX
#f4c01e

LOGO

Primary logotype

Our logo is our most recognizable asset. That's why we love it, are protective of it and ask you to follow the rules when you use it.

Here are different ways to use the logotype on light or dark background.

The monochromatic logotype should only be used when there are not enough colors to properly reproduce the Primary logotype.

Primary logotype

Monochromatic logotype on white background

Original logotype on dark background

Monochromatic logotype on black or dark background

LOGO

Horizontal logotype

If it's impossible to use the Primary logotype for some reason, you have the option of using the Horizontal logotype.

The monochromatic logotype should only be used when there are not enough colors to properly reproduce the Primary logotype.

Horizontal logotype

Monochromatic horizontal logotype on white or light background

Horizontal logotype on dark background

Monochromatic horizontal logotype on black or dark background

LOGO

Size & clearspaces

In order to preserve the integrity of the Primary logotype, it is important that no other logos, type or other graphic elements infringe on its space. The minimum clearspace around the logotype is equivalent to $1/3$ of the width of the logotype.

Smallest size use

The minimum size the Primary logo-type may be used for print applications is 0.6" (15mm) wide. Include the registration mark for this measurement.

Minimum print size 0.6 inch (15 mm) wide.
Minimum digital size 50 pixels wide.

LOGO

Typography

As with our logo, consistent use of our corporate typeface is Avenir Next Bold.

Avenir Next Heavy, can be use for titles.

Avenir Next Bold

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz

0123456789 /()'.,:?!&@#%*

Avenir Next Heavy

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz

0123456789 /()'.,:?!&@#%*

LOGO

Typography

As for body type font of the text we use the Arial Regular.

Use Arial Bold for subtitles.

Arial Regular

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789 /()'.:;!&@#€%*

Arial Italic

*abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789 /()'.:;!&@#€%**

Arial Bold

**abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789 /()'.:;!&@#€%***

Arial Bold

***abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789 /()'.:;!&@#€%****

LOGO

Coordination with background

The primary logotype should be displayed in light background without too many details.

When displaying on a details photographic image background, the monochromatic white or monochromatic black logotype should be used.

yellopix- www.yellopix.be

Annex III. CODECS DECO guidelines

Introduction

The following style guide sets out standard and preferred forms to be used in all CODECS written materials. It aims to provide for a consistent approach to English grammar, spelling and presentation in all CODECS written materials. Given the impossibility to be comprehensive, this style guide aims to provide clarity on those questions that provoke frequent inconsistency, confusion or mistakes. The guide can be updated to provide further clarity.

British English: Prefer British English and try to remember to set your spellchecker to “English (United Kingdom)” to stop Word ‘helpfully’ enforcing or encouraging American English. We are working with programmes and organisations, not programs and organizations.

The style of others: When quoting another source, respect their usage even where it conflicts with our agreed CODECS style.

CODECS Communications group

CODECS has created a Communications Team within the consortium, composed of at least one member for partner organisation. The Comms Team aims to ensure a better coordination of the communication effort, particularly at regional and national level. The Comms Team has a specific channel on the CODECS Microsoft Teams space.

Maximise CODECS Impact

Partners need to use the Microsoft Teams workspace for internal interaction and communication within the project. It has a great importance for sharing content with our members and Work Package leaders, so everyone is kept in the loop. Partners can make the Communications Group aware of information, inputs or ideas by simply sharing them on the channel. In this way, all members responsible to disseminate and communicate further, are aware of potential content to share via several channels.

There are several ways for partners sharing relevant content for CODECS and maximise its communication, dissemination and outreach:

- **Use CODECS social media accounts:** partners can either directly send to the Communications team a message through the specific Social Media channel (message on Facebook, Twitter or LinkedIn) or simply tag the project account in your post or picture (@HORIZONCODECS). The team will receive a notification and will be able to share/retweet it.
- **Share content for the news & events section of the website.** The Communications team will keep the news & events section updated. Partners can share relevant information with the Comms team to be shared through the CODECS website.
- **Make use of the project’s newsletter.** The project newsletter will include featured content generated by partners, such as short articles (500-700 words maximum) on topics relevant for CODECS.
- **Share information and outcomes of your work.** This can be related to the Living Labs, Demo Farms, participation in events, important milestones achieved, or newsworthy information very relevant for CODECS. A two-way communication between partners and the Communications team is a core principle, to promote all content from CODECS further in different ways, including that developed at grassroots level (often missed in communication of this types of EU project).

CODECS style guide

What	How to avoid common mistakes
Acronyms	<p>At the beginning of your text, always write in full with the acronym in brackets in order to make the reader familiar with them, e.g. <i>The Living Lab (LL) held... In CODECS, LL members...</i></p> <p>Try to avoid overuse of acronyms. Occasional re-use of the full expression is preferable to overuse of the acronym.</p> <p>Acronyms in the plural take a small s, e.g. <i>there are 6 LLs</i></p> <p>NOTE: acronyms take a small s even when written in all-CAPS (for example in a title) e.g. <i>TEN NEW LLs JOIN THE PROJECT</i></p>
agenda	Use the standard form agendas as the plural form of the singular agenda
agri-	Prefer use of the hyphen after the prefix agri- , e.g. <i>agri-environment, agri-business</i>
Apostrophes	<p>Most common uses:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possessive form: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>This is Paul's pen</i> (standard form: noun + apostrophe + s). ○ <i>That is James' pen</i> (no s after the apostrophe for a noun already ending in s). ○ <i>The countries' objectives</i> (apostrophe after the s in plural for). Note the important distinction between <i>the cow's field</i> and <i>the cows' field</i>. • Contractions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>It can't work. It won't work.</i> <p>NOTE: never use contractions in formal written English (personal work emails are OK) unless quoting somebody. It is too informal.</p> <p>NOTE: Neither the plural form of an acronym nor the name decade have an apostrophe before the s. e.g. <i>All the latest LLs were approved in the 2020s.</i></p>
and	Use the full word 'and' and not the symbol '&'
Benefiting	Prefer the use of 'benefiting', avoid double t. Be consistent throughout the text
Bio-	Do not use a hyphen with the prefix bio-, e.g. <i>biofuel, bioeconomy, bioenergy, biodiversity</i>
Bullet point list	<p>For lists of short items (without main verbs) the full list and introduction can be presented as simply as possible with no full sentences and no punctuation until the final full stop.</p> <p>e.g. <i>EU Member States beginning with the letter L:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Latvia</i> • <i>Lithuania</i> • <i>Luxembourg.</i> <p>If any one item in the list consists of at least one complete sentence, announce the list with a complete sentence and make each bullet point its own grammatical unit, beginning with a capital letter and ending with a full stop - this avoids confusing punctuation.</p> <p>e.g. <i>The project made a number of recommendations:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) <i>National authorities should do a and b.</i> 2) <i>The European Commission should do c and d. This is in accordance with the relevant legislation.</i>

What	How to avoid common mistakes
	<p>3) <i>Stakeholders should do e and f. They should be supported to do this with funding and advice.</i></p> <p>In other cases, use the same punctuation as you would if writing the list in block text rather than a bullet point list i.e. colon, semi-colons, small first letters and full stop.</p> <p><i>e.g. The formal process involves:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>submitting an application in writing;</i> • <i>receiving an invitation to interview;</i> • <i>attending the interview; and</i> • <i>receiving an offer of employment.</i>
<p>Capitalisation</p>	<p>Use capitals with proper names and titles.</p> <p>Capitals can be used to highlight the formal name of something as opposed to its generic description. <i>e.g. the Rural Development Programmes are programmes on rural development.</i></p> <p>Important terms we capitalise in the CODECS context:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CODECS • Maximising the CO-benefits of agricultural Digitalisation through conducive digital ECoSystems • Living Lab(s) • Demo Farms • DECO Taskforce • Responsible Research and Innovation • Knowledge Accelerator • CAP Network(s) • DG AGRI • European Commission • European Parliament • Member States • CORDIS <p>BUT European organisations, non-governmental organisations</p> <p>NOTE: ‘e.g.’ and ‘i.e.’ are never capitalised and always take points.</p> <p><u>Days, Months but seasons</u></p> <p><i>e.g. a Tuesday in June, during the summer.</i></p> <p><u>Compass points</u></p>

What	How to avoid common mistakes
	<p>Points of the compass (<i>north, north-west, etc.</i>) and their derived forms (<i>north-western etc.</i>) are not capitalised unless they form part of a proper name.</p> <p>e.g. <i>South Africa, Northern Ireland</i></p> <p>BUT <i>southern Africa, northern France.</i></p>
Cooperation-	No need to hyphenate cooperation or coordination
Currency	When presenting amounts in euros, you can use either: EUR or €, but ensure consistency within each article. e.g. <i>the budget was €1 234 000</i> OR <i>the budget was EUR 1 234 000</i>
Dashes	<p>en- dash is a short dash</p> <p>Use CTRL + - (on the numeric keypad)</p> <p>En dashes replace the 'to' in 1–10.</p> <p>em— dash is a long dash</p> <p>Use CTRL + ALT + - (on the numeric keypad)</p> <p>Em dashes break up sentences — like this.</p> <p>Hyphen- (see more details below)</p> <p>This is hyphen-in-action</p>
Database	One word!
Dates	Prefer simplicity, just stating day, month and year; avoid the extra elements (<i>the, th, etc.</i>) that are part of spoken English. e.g. <i>The event will be held on 10 August 2015.</i>
Digitalisation/ Digitisation	Prefer <i>digitalisation</i> , but never with z.
e-	<p>In IT expressions e- is always lower case (avoid use at the start of a sentence if possible) and hyphenated, e.g. <i>e-commerce</i>.</p> <p>EXCEPTION: email</p>
e.g.	e.g. is always written with small letters and points and means 'for example'.
Factsheet	Prefer spelling as one word.
Focus	focus, focused, focusing with a single s.
grams	Write <i>gram, kilogram</i> (not <i>gramme, kilogramme</i>).
grassroots	no need to hyphenate.
greenhouse gases	<p><i>greenhouse gases</i> is shortened to <i>GHGs</i>.</p> <p><i>greenhouse gas emissions</i> is shortened to: <i>GHG emissions</i>.</p>
Hyphenation	<p>The use of hyphens can be a bit of an art form. Nevertheless, some clear ground rules should be followed. The first rule of thumb is to avoid the hyphen if you can, but always use it where it avoids confusion or clunky English. Often hyphens get dropped when the word becomes more commonly used. It is not always a case of the hyphen's use being 'right' or 'wrong'.</p> <p>e.g. <i>prefer co-decision and co-responsibility, but cooperation and coordination</i></p> <p>Take care when use or otherwise of the hyphen actually changes the meaning of what you are trying to say.</p>

What	How to avoid common mistakes
	<p>e.g. <i>recover</i> means to get back or return to a normal state of health; <i>re-cover</i> means to put a new cover on or cover again.</p> <p>Prefer use of the hyphen between two vowels e.g. <i>reduce and recycle, but re-use...</i></p> <p>Except when very frequent usage permits e.g. <i>cooperation</i></p> <p>Hyphenate when two or more terms form one adjective before a noun, but not when they come after the noun. e.g. <i>We need to think of the long term to ensure long-term success.</i> e.g. <i>The document is up to date. It is an up-to-date document.</i></p> <p>NOTE: if in doubt, ask whether each term before the noun describes the noun on its own. For example: the big, red ball is a big ball and a red ball; but the high-level group is not a high group and a level group.</p> <p>NOTE: with adverbs ending in -ly, no hyphen is needed. e.g. <i>the environmentally friendly policy, the mutually beneficial agreement.</i></p> <p>With other adverbs, a hyphen is usually required: e.g. <i>a well-known person in the above-mentioned report</i></p> <p>Do not hyphenate phrasal verbs (e.g. to put on, to take over) but they are often hyphenated or form a single word when they form a noun. e.g. <i>I will follow up with David; I will ensure the follow-up with David.</i> <i>The company was taken over. There was a company takeover.</i></p>
<p>i.e.</p>	<p><i>i.e.</i> is always written with small letters and points and means ‘that is’ e.g. <i>Respect your parents i.e. your mother and father</i></p>
<p>in order to</p>	<p>Prefer simplicity. You rarely need the full expression ‘in order to’. I did x in order to achieve y is the same as I did x to achieve y. e.g. <i>I wrote the guide to help your writing.</i> e.g. <i>They launched the campaign to raise awareness of x.</i></p> <p>However, use the full expression when it avoids possible confusion or changes the meaning. e.g. <i>I asked them to include different perspectives</i> is not the same as <i>I asked them in order to include different perspectives.</i></p>
<p>its / it’s</p>	<p><i>it’s</i> <u>always</u> means <i>it is</i>.</p> <p>The possessive form (<i>its</i>) does not take an apostrophe. e.g. <i>It’s surprising, but the organisation has not yet defined its priorities.</i></p>

What	How to avoid common mistakes
	NOTE: we should never use the informal form <i>it's</i> in our formal publications/emails etc.
Less v fewer	If you can count it, use <i>fewer</i> . If you can't count it, use <i>less</i> . <i>e.g. Farmers are producing less milk / Farmers are producing fewer litres of milk.</i> NOTE: if in doubt, ask whether you can have two of them. Two litres? Yes. Two milks. No.
like	Avoid the use of <i>like</i> when introducing an example. Prefer <i>such as</i> . It avoids confusion with the verb <i>to like</i> and is rather informal. <i>e.g. This involves several Member States, such as France and Germany.</i>
Member States	Always capitalise Member States. Abbreviate on first use to MS. For regions, prefer Flanders (BE) rather than Belgium (Flanders)
metre v meter	A <i>metre</i> is one hundred centimetres. A <i>meter</i> is an instrument that measures, for example, electricity or water consumption.
Multi-funding	Hyphenate multi-funded project, use of multi-funding etc.
n/a	n/a is the short form for "not available", "not applicable" OR "no answer" for use particularly in tables and lists.
No.	You can use No. as an abbreviation of number in a table. However, always remember to put the full stop, otherwise you are just writing the word 'no', which is quite literally a negative thing to do.
Numbers	<p>In large numbers (i.e. above one thousand), do not use decimal points or commas between groups of 3 numbers. Instead, use a half space (this is typed by holding down Ctrl, Shift and the Space bar). If you make the formatting symbols visible, it appears as a raised circle between the numbers. <i>e.g. one million is written as: 1 000 000</i></p> <p>Small integers (whole numbers) of ten or less should be written in full. EXCEPT when the number forms part of a name <i>e.g. we have two priorities in Year 3; there are eight participants in Workshop 5</i></p> <p>In numbers given to decimal places, use a decimal point (generally prefer giving numbers to one decimal place as the right amount of accuracy, but common sense can apply). <i>e.g. on average rural families have 2.3 children</i> <i>e.g. the regional funds for France account for 25.4 % of all the national budget</i></p> <p>Billion. The use of billion to designate thousand million (rather than million million) is now officially recognised by the Commission and is standard usage in official EU publications.</p> <p>When two numbers are adjacent, spell out one of them: <i>e.g. 90 fifty-gram weights OR ninety 50 g weights</i></p>

What	How to avoid common mistakes
	<p>Time spans: for time spans between two years, e.g. 2014-2020</p> <p>NOTE: 2015-2016 is two years. A 12-month period across two years is denoted with a slash e.g. the project year 2015/2016</p> <p>Starting a sentence: never start a sentence with a number written as a figure. Always write the number in full, or restructure the sentence so that the number does not appear at the beginning.</p>
ongoing	prefer simplicity, no need for a hyphen (on-going).
online	never hyphenated.
organisation	never with z.
No one	Spell as two words, but no one will be surprised if you spell it incorrectly. If it helps, remember that no one spells noon with an e on the end.
per cent	<p>Prefer per cent as two words when written in full or use the % sign with a figure. As with units, prefer the half-space between the number and % sign.</p> <p>e.g. <i>Twenty per cent of people are clever. That means that 80 % are not.</i></p>
Person / people	<p>The plural form of <i>person</i> is <i>people</i>.</p> <p>Persons is EU-speak.</p>
Policy-makers	Hyphenated: also decision-makers, opinion-formers, etc...
Publications	<p>If you quote a publication title in the text, use single quotation marks.</p> <p>e.g. <i>The European Commission released the revised 'EU Bioeconomy Strategy'</i></p> <p>If you provide bibliographic references (e.g. in footnotes):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> For books, reports, studies etc. use the format N. Surname (date) Title, Publisher, link e.g. A. Christie (1934), <i>Murder on the Orient Express</i>, Collins, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Agatha_Christie_bibliography For articles from publications use N. Surname, Title of the article, Title of the Journal n° (date): page numbers, link if available <p>e.g. P. Panagos, <i>Cost of agricultural productivity loss due to soil erosion in the European Union</i>, Land degradation & development 29.3 (2018): 471-484.</p>
Quotations	<p>Words that are missing from the quote but needed to make sense of it can be inserted in [square brackets]. For example, <i>if the Commissioner is asked about the CAP and says "It is very important."</i> You can quote him as saying "[The CAP] is very important."</p> <p>If necessary, you may mark errors with '[sic]'. e.g. <i>"Co-operation is important for all 27 [sic] EU Member States," he said.</i></p>
Quotation marks double	"Quotes go in double quotation marks," said the Communications Manager.

What	How to avoid common mistakes
	<p>If an extract ends with a full stop or question-mark, put the punctuation before the closing quotation marks. Convert full stops to commas if the sentence continues after the quote.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>e.g. The Commissioner believes the event “marks a sea change for rural development in Europe.”</i> • <i>e.g. The event “marks a sea change for rural development in Europe”, said the Commissioner.</i> • <i>e.g. The Commissioner believes the event “marks a sea change” for rural development in Europe.</i> <p>The first letter of a sentence quoted in full should be upper case. <i>e.g. The Commissioner replied, “Every contribution is equally important.”</i></p> <p>Always use a comma before a quotation (see examples above).</p> <p>If you include a footnote to mention the source, add it after the closing quotation marks. <i>e.g. The Commissioner believes the event “marks a sea change for rural development in Europe.”¹</i></p> <p>NOTE: quotation marks change across languages – make sure you’re using English quotation marks (“...”) if you’re writing in English!</p>
<p>Quotation marks single</p>	<p>Single quotations marks can be used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For quotes within a quote, <i>e.g. “The Commissioner believes this is an ‘extremely urgent’ issu”, said the DG AGRI spokesman.</i> • For technical terms/jargon – especially on first use, <i>e.g. This is known as ‘gold-plating’.</i> • To recognise that a word is to be understood carefully or not to be taken literally, <i>e.g. There is no ‘right’ or ‘wrong’ way to prepare an CAP Strategic Plan.</i> • To make it clear that multiple words form one concept, <i>e.g. Use good practices in a more strategic way based on careful identification, collection, ‘consolidation of learning’ and dissemination</i> • To designate the name/title of a report or publications, etc., <i>e.g. The report ‘Climate delivery within the CAP’ is published...</i>
<p>seasons</p>	<p>No capitals for spring, summer, autumn, winter (even though days of the week, months are capitalised).</p>
<p>training</p>	<p>training is an abstract noun in the same way education is so it does not exist in the plural form. You cannot have two educations and you cannot have two trainings. Rather, you can have <i>two training events</i> or <i>training workshops</i>, etc.</p>
<p>Titles and sources</p>	<p>Title for tables and figures should appear at the top of the mentioned table or figure. The source of information needs to be added at the bottom of the table or figure.</p>

What	How to avoid common mistakes
Tonnes	Write <i>tonnes</i> and not <i>tons</i> .
Units	<p>When using the abbreviated form of a unit, prefer the use of the half-space between the number and the unit. Write the half-space by typing CTR-Shift-Space - e.g. <i>the farm covered 350 ha</i></p> <p>Short forms of units are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • billion – bn, million - mm • euros - EUR or € (e.g. €30 or EUR 30) • gram – g, kilogram – kg • hectare- ha • kilometre – km, metre – m
Use v utilise	Prefer simplicity. Prefer <i>use</i> to <i>utilise</i>
Z versus S	Always prefer – <i>ise</i> endings to – <i>ize</i> endings and – <i>isation</i> to – <i>ization</i> . e.g. <i>prioritise, organise, organisation, urbanisation</i>

Writing short articles

Either the Communications Team or the project partners can propose a topic and author for a potential article for publication. The articles will be 500-700 words long and will focus on the main project concepts, messages, Living Labs, Demo Farms, or other initiatives emerging at regional, national or EU level that are of relevance. To plan an article, first think of your main message or story, then write down 3-4 key messages, putting them in order of importance.

Think of your target audience. These articles will be read by:

- Researchers and academics
- SMEs
- Public authorities
- Citizens
- Digital technology operators
- Other Horizon 2020 projects
- Policy or Desk officers from the European institutions
- Farmers and agricultural workers

With such general audiences it is important to stick to general guidelines above: be concise, clear and focused. Keep the language simple, minimise jargon and spell out any acronyms on first use. To ensure you include the most important information, use the journalistic technique of the “5 Ws” – explain: who, what, when, where and why. Make the article engaging and interesting. Use short sentences and animate the text with data, information, examples and quotes from key people. Images, charts, photos and graphics can help keep readers engaged. Keep the tone positive and use active language. Make use of the CODECSA style guide ensuring that you use all concepts and spellings in a consistent way with all materials produced in the framework of the project.

Process

Before you start writing an article to submit to CODECS, discuss your proposal with the Communications Officer, to establish clear deadlines and timing, as well as some general directions. Once you have submitted the draft, this will be reviewed and any queries raised will be addressed to you. When the process is finalised, the featured article will be ready

for publishing on the website, share through social media and, depending on the outline of the newsletter, included in one of the editions.

Writing a press release

What's New?

The challenge here is knowing what happened. Your first step should be a catchy headline:

Headlines should be short, but they need to grab the attention. You may also want to add a subheading with extra detail. After that, your first full paragraph should set out all the key information that you need to communicate. This can then be expanded upon in the next paragraphs.

Why Does This Matter?

What consequences does it have? Why do people need to know? And most importantly, what do you want to achieve by spreading this news? Keep it short and focus on these issues.

Who Are the Key Players?

Essentially, you may want to mention anyone to whom your news is relevant! In addition, press releases are most effective when targeted at a particular audience, so think about who you will send the press release to so you can tailor it accordingly.

When and Where?

If your news is specific to a time and place (e.g. a one-off event in a particular town), you will need to include this in your press release. But you also need to consider the timing of your press release. The timing should be related to what you want to achieve. For coverage in the run-up to an event, send the press release 3-5 days before you want the news to appear (you can include an embargo to ensure it doesn't go out early). If you want coverage about something that has already happened, send it as soon as possible afterwards.

How Did This Happen?

This is about fleshing out your headline and opening paragraph by giving some background information. This might be for instance past instances of a similar event. The key is to make this information quotable, and one way to do this is to include a quote in the press release. Include one key figure in a short sound bite.

If you can cover all these points, the content of your press release should be pretty much perfect. All you need to do now is write it up, get it proofread and send it out!